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**Initial definition of the scientific challenges and
initial evaluation plan - Enabling next-generation
plasma accelerators for real world applications with
PIConGPU**

WP 1: Plasma Simulations - Codes and Grand Challenges

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Executive Summary

Laser-plasma accelerators (LPA) have been demonstrated to provide beams of unprecedented properties such as ultrashort nanocoulomb electron beams at the GeV energy scale suitable as drivers for coherent free electron lasers (FELs). The interaction of Petawatt class lasers such as the Dresden laser acceleration source (DRACO) operated at Helmholtz-Zentrum Dresden – Rossendorf (HZDR) with matter creates plasmas of unique properties that, with help of new instruments such as the Helmholtz International Beamline for Extreme Fields (HIBEF, www.hibef.eu) at the European XFEL (EU-XFEL, www.xfel.eu) can be studied at atomistic resolution. This opens up new capabilities to study laser-plasma interaction relevant to challenging applications such as laser-driven inertial confinement fusion.

The Helmholtz Association’s ATHENA distributed facility (www.athena-helmholtz.de) provides access to this cutting-edge technology on a national and international scale. The Extreme Light Infrastructure (ELI, www.eli-laser.eu) and the network of specialized laser facilities, Laserlab Europe (www.laserlab-europe.eu), have put Europe at the international forefront of this innovative technology. This has been recognized by the international community, and with LaserNet US similar initiatives in the United States of America and new facilities such as SACLA in Japan have been set up.

Laser-plasma interaction (LPI) and its applications have from the beginning been driven by a strong, fruitful interplay between simulation and experiment. Now, with the use of machine learning and artificial intelligence a further fusion of experiment and simulation and thus a transformation of the operation of large-scale research facilities has come in reach.

For this to work, central simulation codes such as PIconGPU have to make optimum use of future computing technologies such as exascale computing. In the Plasma Exascale-Performance Simulations Center of Excellence we will study a new accelerator technology, Traveling-Wave Electron Acceleration (TWEAC), that has the potential to provide a scalable acceleration scheme towards ultra-brilliant, high quality electron beams at the TeV energy scale.

We provide a figure of merit as the weighted sum of the total number of particle updates per second (90 %) and the number of cell updates per second (10 %) and its current scaling on top 10 high performance computer systems such as Summit and Frontier. With scalability of the code to the full capacity of these systems demonstrated, adapting the code to new hardware accelerator technologies provided by the European Processor Initiative (EPI) within the EuroHPC ecosystem will be the focus of our work, using the alpaka suite for single source heterogeneous computing for portable parallel programming developed by HZDR. Furthermore, data-intense workflows for efficient checkpointing, Exascale I/O and in-memory code coupling using the openPMD ecosystem will be investigated to make optimum use of the data produced at future European exascale systems.

Contents

1	Introduction	6
2	Definition of the Scientific Challenge	6
2.1	Relevance and Physical Background	7
2.2	Detailed Definition of the Simulation Setup	10
3	Gap analysis	12
3.1	Downscaling the Target Case	12
3.2	Initial Performance Analysis	12
4	Roadmap for Development	13
4.1	Identification of Bottlenecks in the Current Code	13
4.1.1	Performance-portability to novel European exascale compute architectures	13
4.1.2	I/O capabilities to optimally exploit memory layouts of European exascale systems	14
4.1.3	In-transit data analysis to tackle the data deluge	14
4.2	Test suite for continuous integration and code interface for automatization to secure fidelity of physics results in code development	15
4.3	Next Steps Planned	15
4.3.1	Extend, test and fine-tune I/O capabilities to optimally exploit memory capabilities in European exascale systems	15
4.3.2	Extend and test streaming capability in PIConGPU using openPMD/A-DIOS2 to be used in production	16
4.3.3	Provide test suite for continuous integration and provide scriptable PIConGPU interface (pyPIConGPU) for automatization	16
4.3.4	Develop, test and fine-tune alpaka backend for European exascale compute architectures (postponed until access to a system is provided)	16
5	Software Engineering Status and Plan	16
5.1	Code management/version control	16
5.2	Continuous integration	17
5.3	Testing	17
5.4	Deployment	17
5.5	Documentation	17
5.6	Release strategy	17
5.7	Requirements management	18
5.8	Issue tracking	18
5.9	Dependencies/Prerequisites	18
5.10	Development and Deployment towards Exascale	18
6	Conclusion	19

1 Introduction

Laser-plasma accelerators (LPA) provide unique beam properties for both electron and ion beams at a compact infrastructural footprint enabling new applications. Recently, an LPA that drove a coherent, short-wavelength pulses from a seeded free electron laser (FEL) has been demonstrated at Helmholtz-Zentrum Dresden – Rossendorf [1]. In contrast, conventional particle accelerators have almost reached their maximum accelerator gradients within a single cavity due to the fundamental barriers of radio frequency field emission and quench of the accelerator cavities.

Plasma accelerators provide acceleration fields on the order of 1 TV/m and thus 1000 to 10000 times higher than conventional accelerators, enabling highly compact accelerator setups. Typically driven by a high-power laser of petawatt peak power, these accelerators enable unique applications ranging from driving brilliant compact x-ray and gamma-ray radiation sources to high flux radiation therapy for cancer. An all-optical X-ray free electron laser (XFEL) of a few tens of metres in size would be a revolution in X-ray imaging and would democratise this technology, as currently only a few XFELs exist worldwide that are driven by kilometre-long electron accelerators.

In order to use LPAs for such applications one needs a detailed investigation of the non-equilibrium plasma dynamics driven by the high power lasers happening on atomic, subfemtosecond time scale and nanometer length scales. With upcoming large-scale facilities such as the Extreme Light Infrastructure (ELI), the Helmholtz International Beamline for Extreme Fields (HIBEF), the Helmholtz ATHENA distributed facility for plasma accelerators and the many specialized facilities within Laserlab Europe, experimental and simulation results can finally be compared at comparable resolution and detail. Thus, a new era of studying non-equilibrium high energy density (HED) matter with atomic precision and its applications has come within reach.

2 Definition of the Scientific Challenge

The quest for advanced acceleration techniques for providing more compact accelerators is a grand challenge of particle accelerator physics. Addressing this challenge will allow to further scale up energies for high-energy physics, as well as enable accelerator technology to be more compact and commonly available, thus making it affordable for universities, hospitals, and industry to operate their own accelerator facilities.

Particle accelerators have a broad impact on science, engineering, and medicine. State-of-the-art accelerators based on conventional radio-frequency (rf) -cavities are driving the most advanced x-ray FELs such as LCLS.

In contrast, Laser-plasma accelerators (LPA) can make use of orders of magnitude larger acceleration fields in plasma structures than are achievable in conventional rf-cavities. Despite tremendous advances in LPAs with respect to beam energy, quality, charge and stability, sustaining scalability of compact LPAs for accelerating bright electron and positron beams to even higher electron energies is one of the yet to be solved key challenges of the field.

In pioneering studies at HZDR, we found that these limitations can be overcome by a novel laser-plasma interaction geometry, Traveling-Wave Electron Acceleration (TWEAC) [2]. Relying on spatio-temporally shaped ultrashort, high-power laser pulses using existing

laser technology, these laser pulses provide "flying" focal regions propagating at tunable velocities close to the speed of light without the need for laser guiding structures.

TWEAC is the first LPA approach to circumvent the three basic LPA limitations (dephasing, depletion and defocusing) simultaneously. This allows to choose the LPA plasma density and the length of an accelerator independent of these three limitations and makes new regimes accessible. Furthermore, TWEAC eliminates the need for staging, which requires particle beam transport and a new laser beam for each stage. In contrast, standard laser-wakefield accelerators would require over 10 to 100s of stages with an equal number of laser beams and particle beam transports – prone to severe charge loss and emittance degradation – before reaching the TeV (tera-electron-volt)-scale. With TWEAC the number of stages could be strongly reduced, or completely eliminated.

Particularly for electron and positron energies beyond 10GeV, on the 100GeV to TeV-scale, TWEAC could become a game changer for high-energy physics and would put TeV-scale electron energies at GeV/cm acceleration gradients within reach of ELI-type laser facilities. The feasibility of LPAs for multi-TeV scale high-energy physics is a community-encompassing, multi-decade challenge with many open questions. Leveraging the rich compute resources of Exascale HPC systems to model TWEAC could pave the way to energy-scalable LPAs that reach the highest particle energies at the energy frontier.

The primary goal of our research is to obtain a detailed understanding of the laser-plasma dynamics of different TWEAC accelerator regimes. Here, we aim to understand the dynamics of cavity formation, TWEACs luminal shock front and the energy transfer efficiency from laser to particle beams. Secondly, for generating bright particle beams, we aim to study electron injection mechanisms unique to TWEAC.

2.1 Relevance and Physical Background

Whether and how LPAs could be scaled up and used for electron-positron colliders at multiple TeV energies [3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8] is an unanswered question. Three fundamental limitations determine design and scalability of laser-plasma accelerators [9, 10].

1. Dephasing: The laser pulse in plasma is slower than the accelerated electrons, so that these outrun the accelerating field after a characteristic distance.
2. Depletion: Within another characteristic distance scale the laser transfers its complete energy to the accelerating plasma wave, hence terminating the acceleration process.
3. Diffraction: When a laser beam defocuses, the laser intensity becomes too low to continue sustaining the plasma wave and thus electron acceleration.

While the limits 1) and 2) occur earlier at high-plasma densities, 3) becomes an issue particularly at low densities $< 10^{17} \text{ cm}^{-3}$, when plasma-based laser guiding diminishes. For mitigating 1) and 2), all high-energy LPAs currently have to operate at low plasma densities. However, this requires higher laser pulse energies, while resulting in lower acceleration gradients. Currently 10 GeV are the practical limit for a single LWFA. For the last ten years, LPA research has thus been focusing on enabling and improving staging, where one electron beam is consecutively accelerated by multiple laser-wakefield stages, each driven by a separate laser pulse in a separate gas target. Despite recent successes

with two stages [11] – the goal being tens to hundreds of stages – synchronization and beam transport challenges degrade beam charge, beam emittance and shot-to-shot stability. One practical challenge is that a minimum distance in-between the stages is required to collinearly couple-out the spent laser and couple-in a new laser pulse for the next stage, while the electron bunch passes through unperturbed. All above considerations strongly constrain every LPA design at high-energies. Even if one functional accelerator design was found, it would be hard to adjust plasma density or acceleration length without degrading its performance.

The major goal of TWEAC is to simultaneously circumvent aforementioned three limits, so that more regimes become accessible and LPAs can be readily adjusted to a particular application – not the other way around. By adding such scalability to LPAs, this will enable high-electron energy LPAs beyond 10 GeV without staging and high-repetition rate LPAs using less charge per laser pulse.

Traveling-wave electron acceleration (TWEAC) [2] is a novel laser-plasma accelerator concept, which removes aforementioned three limits in plasma-based accelerator physics to make compact accelerators more scalable and adaptable. With TWEAC it becomes possible to attain sustainable, steady-state acceleration in plasma-based accelerators, scalable with respect to plasma density, laser pulse energy, accelerator length and final electron energy reached. This will make new LPA regimes accessible, enhancing the ability to tailor plasma-based accelerators to specific applications for science, medicine and industry applications. Particularly, this makes it possible to reach electron energies beyond 10 GeV without the need for LWFA staging, strongly reducing electron beam transport challenges. Such compact and versatile electron accelerators and x-ray light sources could help boost availability and affordability of accelerator technology for universities, hospitals and industry by enabling them to operate their own facilities. On a medium time-scale, TWEAC could enable high-repetition rate 1 GeV-scale electron beams based on 10 TW laser systems. On a longer-term horizon, TWEAC could be a key technique for scaling-up LPA accelerators up to the energy frontier enabling electron-positron colliders at multi-TeV energies [3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8]. This directly addresses one of the grand challenges in accelerator physics of providing feasible, yet affordable Large-Hadron Collider (LHC) successors for high-energy physics to unravel the fundamental questions of the universe.

TWEAC uses two pulse front-tilted lasers focused onto a longitudinally extended plasma target (Fig. 1), such that a confined focal region at the intersection of the two lasers moves along the line-focus and drives a plasma wakefield capable of accelerating an electron bunch at a high acceleration gradient [2]. Tuning the pulse-front tilt ensures that the wake is driven at the vacuum speed of light rather than the lower plasma group velocity dominating established LWFAs, hence avoiding that accelerated electrons outrun the wake. The lateral coupling-in and -out of the laser, ensures that there is always a yet unused portion of the laser entering an unperturbed part of the plasma target. Every such portion of the laser then traverses the plasma target sideways, transfers its energy to the plasma wake and subsequently exits the plasma at the other side. Such continuous laser insertion and extraction circumvents the depletion limit and the use of staging.

Although TWEAC’s potential as a scalable laser plasma accelerator has been theoretically demonstrated in [2], its prime advantage of straightforward scalability to accelerate electron beams to beyond 10 GeV has not been shown yet, due to the lack of compute

Figure 1: Traveling-Wave Electron Acceleration (TWEAC) features a laser-plasma interaction region, which propagates with exactly the speed of light, thus remaining synchronized to the accelerated electron bunch arbitrarily far beyond the dephasing length – limited by the spatial extent of the laser pulse only. (a) illustrates the comoving laser overlap, as well as the laser field cycling through the laser-plasma interaction region. (b) depicts the cylindrical focusing geometry. (c) shows a zoomed-in schematic of the accelerating region. The two TWEAC lasers (red intensity contours) drive a copropagating V-shaped plasma cavity with $v_{\text{laser}} < v_{\text{beam}} < v_{\text{cavity}} \equiv c$ that accelerates an electron bunch in its longitudinal cavity field (orange-white-purple). (d) illustrates in overview the combined geometry of two ultrashort, pulse-front tilted, obliquely incident laser beams in a line focus, driving a wakefield in a slit-nozzle generated gas jet for accelerating an electron bunch.

resources. The first simulation of a 1 GeV TWEAC accelerator at limited resolution took more than 40 days time-to-solution on 196 NVIDIA-k80 GPUs. For the same reason, more extended theoretical studies – such as identifying optimal regimes, investigating unique interaction dynamics, comparing different particle injection mechanisms, as well as the challenge to also accelerate positron beams – so far were limited in scope. We plan to extensively study TWEAC on exascale compute resources to unravel its unique properties and demonstrate how these can be optimally exploited to provide scalable electron and positron acceleration beyond 10 GeV using existing laser technology.

In summary, our physics challenge is to explore TWEAC. Specifically, we want to address with our simulations:

- Identify the most suitable TWEAC regimes for stable acceleration.
- Demonstrate acceleration of electrons in a single stage beyond 10 GeV with TWEAC.
- Assess which injection techniques for standard LPAs can be employed for TWEAC.
- Evaluate possibilities for injection of high-brightness electrons.
- Explore new capabilities of TWEAC with respect to electron injection techniques.

2.2 Detailed Definition of the Simulation Setup

The target simulation setup will have a plasma number density in the region of $10^{18}/\text{cm}^3$ to $10^{19}/\text{cm}^3$. Since the spatial scale of plasma density fluctuations due to a disturbance (such as a laser pulse in our case) is inversely proportional to the initial plasma density, the following detailed estimates of simulation size will assume a plasma number density n_e on the lower end of the mentioned range, i. e. $n_e = 0.5 \times 10^{18}/\text{cm}^3$.

With the scale for spatial plasma density fluctuations being given by the plasma oscillation length $\lambda_p = 2\pi c \sqrt{\epsilon_0 m_e / (n_e e^2)}$, the diameter d_B of the accelerating plasma cavities can be estimated with $d_B \simeq (2\sqrt{a_0}/\pi)\lambda_p$ [9] and is seen to be directly proportional to the plasma oscillation length. In the planned simulation we will focus on a combined laser strength $a_0 < 10$ in the laser overlap region such that $d_B \sim 2\lambda_p$ is used as an estimate for the spatial scale of the plasma cavity. In order to not cut off any important plasma dynamics in front of the laser pulse and behind the first cavity, we assume a longitudinal extent (i. e. along the electron propagation direction y) of our simulation volume of $10\lambda_p$, about $500 \mu\text{m}$ for a $0.5 \times 10^{18}/\text{cm}^3$ plasma. This also accounts for a reduction of the actual simulation window extent along y compared to the simulation volume extent along y due to the moving window implementation in PIConGPU.

The simulation volume's transverse extents along x and y directions are mainly determined by the laser field spatial extent and its change during propagation through the focus. As the focal line of the cylindrical laser focus is aligned with the electron propagation direction y , the laser propagation direction is in the y - z -plane in the simulation. Due to (de-)focusing, the laser's width depends only on its distance from the focal line along the z -axis.

Since well evacuated plasma cavities are expected for laser focal widths $w_{x,0}$ of the order of the plasma oscillation length, $w_{x,0} \sim \lambda_p$, we assume $w_{x,0} = 10 \mu\text{m}$ resulting in a Rayleigh length of about $z_R = 400 \mu\text{m}$ for a laser wavelength of $\lambda_0 = 800 \text{ nm}$. With the laser pulse significantly evolving over a Rayleigh length, and accordingly the plasma response, we aim for a laser propagation of about 2 Rayleigh length before it reaches the focus. That is the simulation volume's extent along the z -axis is about $1600 \mu\text{m}$.

The simulation volume's extent along the x -axis is determined by the evolution of the laser pulse width while it travels through the line focus, given by $w_x(z)/w_{x,0} = [1 + (z/z_R)^2]^{1/2}$. At the simulation boundary, i. e. at two Rayleigh length from the focal line, the laser pulse width increased by about a factor of 2.5 to $w_x(2z_R) = 25 \mu\text{m}$. In order to fit the full Gaussian pulse field into the simulation domain, the volume's extent along the x -axis needs to be $12 \times w_x(2z_R) = 500 \mu\text{m}$.

For the computation of the laser-plasma interaction by the particle-in-cell method the simulation domain is divided into cells with the plasma and fields temporal evolution therein being iteratively advanced in time steps. Both spatial and temporal resolution must be chosen to sample the scales of variation several times in order to correctly resolve the physics of the interaction. With the shortest spatial and temporal scale being given by the laser wavelength λ_0 and its period λ_0/c , respectively, we chose a grid resolution along the main propagation direction of the laser of $\Delta y = \lambda_0/15 = 0.0533 \mu\text{m}$. For the resolution along the transverse directions x and z , we need to take into account the range of our envisaged parameters. First, we want to study the plasma cavity properties and injection dynamics for laser width down to the scale of the laser wavelength. Second, we

want to study the plasma cavity properties and injection dynamics for plasma number densities up to $10^{19}/\text{cm}^3$, where we additionally need to take into account that the laser ponderomotive force can compress the plasma to densities 10 times the initial density in front of the laser as can be seen in fig. 2 further below. This leads to plasma oscillation length on the micron scale. i.e. of the order of the laser wavelength again. In total, we therefore choose a resolution along the transverse directions of twice the longitudinal resolution, $\Delta x = \Delta z = 2\Delta y = 0.1067\mu\text{m}$. This relatively small asymmetry in cell extensions along the axes will also aid in keeping the anisotropy in phase speed of the Maxwell solver small which will lead to wrong laser field dynamics and dispersion of the laser pulse when becoming large.

From these considerations, the temporal resolution is given by the Courant-Friedrich-Levy condition [12] for finite-difference time-domain methods used to solve Maxwell's equations,

$$\Delta t = 0.995 \left[\Delta x^{-2} + \Delta y^{-2} + \Delta z^{-2} \right]^{-1/2} / c = 0.145 \text{ fs}.$$

Performing particle-in-cell simulations with as many as possible macro-particles, which sample the distribution of plasma particles in spatial and momentum space, is important to reduce the uncertainty on estimates for the physical properties of the plasma after some simulation time. As we want to predict the final properties of the accelerated electron bunch as well as the properties of the injected electrons for the injection studies with high physical fidelity, we will sample the initial plasma density with 8 macro-particles per cell.

Simulation run time depends on the type of milestone simulation. Parameter scan and injection study simulations will run until the laser-plasma interaction reaches a steady state after initial electron injection. We expect to be required to simulate a time frame of 5 ps until this state is reached, including an initial slow upramp of the plasma density. This corresponds to about 34600 k time steps the simulation needs to run.

Our prime concern is the growth of numerical errors of the field solver in the course of interaction. Almost certainly they will reach a level where they substantially alter the laser-plasma interaction. We will therefore employ a tenth-order finite-difference time-domain method with greatly improved numerical dispersion properties [13] in comparison to the standard second order method. Higher-order methods come at a cost of smaller time steps for stable operation. We estimate the required time step to be $\Delta t = 0.087 \text{ fs}$ in order to keep the error in the central wavelength's propagation distance below 15% of the plasma oscillation length after propagation over a distance of the Rayleigh length along the z -axis for a $\phi = 5^\circ$ case. The required amount of time steps until acceleration to 11 GeV can be estimated to about 4217 k

In summary, our challenges from the computational resources and numerics point of view are:

- Long-term stability: Simulations of TWEAC beyond 10 GeV will run of the order of 10^6 timesteps. Stability of the solvers, in terms of artificial amplification of noise or small errors, needs to be studied.
- Accuracy: If stability of the simulation setup is given, we want to ensure high-fidelity simulation results, i.e. keep errors due to numerical inaccuracies low. We will use higher order schemes for the solvers, i.e. field solver, particle pusher, and particle shape.

- **Simulation volume size:** Due to the line focus geometry, the laser pulses used in TWEAC have a large width in the plane transverse to the focal plane compared to the cylindrically symmetric laser pulses used in LWFA. In order to capture the plasma cavity formation correctly in the simulation, large plasma volumes have to be simulated. Together with the increased accuracy requirement, this increases the required computational resources by orders of magnitude compared to standard LWFA simulations.

3 Gap analysis

3.1 Downscaling the Target Case

The simulations scenario considered for this performance test and gap analysis is based on TWEAC and employs all necessary code features for simulations of TWEACs. Specifically, this scenario consists of an initially homogeneous distribution of electron-like macro-particles with 25 macro-particles per cell resembling a warm plasma with an electron number density of $0.8e18/\text{cm}^3$, an initial temperature of 0.5 eV, and an initial drift of $0.56c$ along the y -axis. Two pulse-front tilted and obliquely incident laser pulses, as required by TWEAC, propagate through this plasma within the y - z -plane. See fig. 2 for a visualization of a similar but not equal test scenario featuring all necessary setup components.

Figure 2: Visualization of a test setup for a TWEAC simulation where two pulse-front tilted laser pulses propagate through a plasma and where their propagation directions enclose an angle.

3.2 Initial Performance Analysis

PIConGPU has proven scalability on large-scale systems, such as Summit and recently, as one of the OLCF Frontier Center for Accelerated Application Readiness teams, on full Frontier system. The code has been awarded with 1M node hours for an INCITE allocation on Frontier in 2023. Recent weak scaling results of compute performance on Summit are shown in fig. 3a.

A scaling of PIConGPU's Figure of Merit (FOM), i. e. the weighted sum of the total number of particle updates per second (90 %) and the number of cell updates per second

(10%), has been performed on OLCF’s Frontier system to a total of 36864 AMD MI250X GPUs. The result is presented in fig. 3b. In this particular configuration, the simulation size included $2.7 \cdot 10^{13}$ macroparticles in 10^{12} grid cells. This is in comparison to our base FOM run on Summit in 2019 where the simulation size included $1 \cdot 10^{13}$ macroparticles in $4 \cdot 10^{11}$ grid cells. One thousand time-steps completed in a mere 6 and a half minutes. Furthermore, PIConGPU actively develops and integrates I/O workflows for the Tbyte

Figure 3: (a) Weak scaling of PIConGPU from 162 to 27600 GPUs on Summit using the TWEAC test. PIConGPU achieves a weak scaling efficiency $> 95\%$. (b) FOM scaling of PIConGPU from 24 GPUs (6 nodes) to 36864 GPUs (9216 nodes) on Frontier using the TWEAC test case. PIConGPU achieves an average FOM for the largest run of 65.3 TeraUpdates/s

to Pbyte scale. For disk based I/O from PIConGPU, simulation output time is limited by the I/O throughput of the parallel filesystem (PFS) performance, see fig. 4. Making use of openPMD’s streaming capability, an asynchronous I/O workflow can be employed that allows scaling of the perceived throughput beyond the filesystem’s bandwidth limit.

4 Roadmap for Development

4.1 Identification of Bottlenecks in the Current Code

While PIConGPU already successfully demonstrated scaling to the full exascale system Frontier, see performance scaling in sec. 3.2, we identify the following development goals to efficiently produce scientifically relevant results on future European exascale machines.

4.1.1 Performance-portability to novel European exascale compute architectures

alpaka and its CUPLA interface, both developed at HZDR, are used to ensure performance portability of PIConGPU enabling us to run it without modifications on different architectures. Any novel compute architectures in European exascale systems will require a designing or adapting a corresponding alpaka backend.

Figure 4: PIconGPU I/O scaling for different I/O strategies on Summit. While throughput of direct disk-based I/O saturates already at a fraction of the systems size, employing asynchronous I/O via streaming allows scaling of perceived throughput beyond the parallel filesystem’s (PFS) bandwidth limit.

4.1.2 I/O capabilities to optimally exploit memory layouts of European exascale systems

The availability of Checkpoint & Restarting workflows on the next systems will be a requirement for long running, large-scale simulations. Otherwise we risk wasting hours of precious compute time. For example, a simulation that would run normally 4 hours on a system, may experience a node failure (or even a simulation internal failure) after 3 hours. If there is no checkpointing available, one has to run the whole 3 hours of previous simulation time again, instead of restarting from a checkpoint made half or one hour ago.

Currently, one technical limitation with Checkpoint & Restarting is that it requires 2-3 times the memory one actually consumes with pure simulation data due to operations performed on the data, e.g. transformation to/from the data format of the checkpointing library, or de-/compressing, ...). On Frontier, due to its 1:1 ratio of GPU to host memory, this is currently only possible by underutilizing GPUs in terms of available memory capacity in order to have the factor 2-3 available on the host side. Thus one priority is to implement I/O chunking strategies in PIconGPU to enable utilization of the full GPU memory, even when host-side memory is limited. This change will allow running 2-3 times larger physics scenarios.

4.1.3 In-transit data analysis to tackle the data deluge

Another major issue of large-scale simulations is the sheer amount of data. A half system run on Frontier (4600 nodes) making use of half the available GPU memory per node (256 GiB) equates to simulation data of 1.12 Petabyte size. Typically a full simulation

output is performed in regular intervals, in order to analyze the time evolution in terms of particle and field dynamics and their interaction, which becomes unfeasible for these large-scale simulations since file systems with sufficient capacity and speed need to be available to store and load this data. While there is the possibility to directly add C++ code to PIConGPU in form of a plugin which pre-analyzes, slices, partitions, and transforms simulation data prior to writing to disk, the development of such tightly coupled plugins is tedious since typically used analysis tools, such as matplotlib and scipy, are written in python and cannot be used. Furthermore, every simulation is different which introduces an additional overhead by requiring to adapt the plugin code in order to store only the required data.

Up to now, analysis of simulation data takes place by writing independent and comparatively small python scripts, which make use of the above named tools, and work on previously created simulation data. Since this will be hardly possible on future exascale systems, we want to make use of the streaming capability of the ADIOS2 I/O library. It would allow us to loosely couple our existing analysis scripts to the running simulation by rewriting only a few lines of code in the script. In such a workflow, the analysis script would be executed in parallel to the simulation, and simulation data would be directly streamed to the analysis script, without writing the data to disk in between. In the analysis script, the necessary data slicing, partitioning, calculations, and transformations can be performed and only the reduced data is written to disk, much like a tightly-coupled PIConGPU plugin, but without the overhead of in depth C++ development.

4.2 Test suite for continuous integration and code interface for automatization to secure fidelity of physics results in code development

Compute intensive simulations at exascale using newly implemented physics models easily go to waste if the fidelity of the results cannot be tested, i.e. trusted. PIConGPU already provides a basic continuous integration (CI) workflow, proving a suite compilation tests that quickly detects code regressions in development. So far, CI tests does not yet test code functionality or the fidelity of physics predictions. Since any code extension or optimization potentially leads to code regressions, developing and implementing a physics test suite is a critical step before extending PIConGPU with more complex physics models, such as atomic physics models. As an important ingredient for such workflows, PIConGPU has a scriptable interface (pyPIConGPU), which provides automatization-capabilities. This interface still needs to be refined to be used in production.

4.3 Next Steps Planned

4.3.1 Extend, test and fine-tune I/O capabilities to optimally exploit memory capabilities in European exascale systems

In order to save memory on the host side for checkpointing, we will refactor PIConGPU's checkpointing capability to first, directly access the simulation data on the GPU in order to save one full data copy from GPU to host memory, and second, work only on chunks of the simulation data and process these one after another instead of working on the

full data at once. This will reduce the host memory requirements of the I/O library for transformation to the target data format and compression.

4.3.2 Extend and test streaming capability in PICongGPU using openPMD/ADIOS2 to be used in production

We will extend and test streaming capability in PICongGPU leveraging the openPMD and ADIOS2 I/O libraries for production-usage.

4.3.3 Provide test suite for continuous integration and provide scriptable PICongGPU interface (pyPICongGPU) for automatization

We will develop, test and fine-tune a physics test suite for PICongGPU and integrate these into a CI workflow. We will provide a pyPICongGPU-interface to be used in production.

4.3.4 Develop, test and fine-tune alpaka backend for European exascale compute architectures (postponed until access to a system is provided)

Once new target architectures and the programming models of the upcoming European exascale systems are known, we will develop a new alpaka backend or adapt an existing one. Beyond the pure implementation, the backend need to be tested for stability and fine-tuned for performance in the course of the project. We will measure our progress using use the figure-of-merit (FOM) performance indicators of 3.2.

5 Software Engineering Status and Plan

5.1 Code management/version control

PICongGPU and its ecosystem (alpaka, openPMD, etc.) live on public Github repositories: <https://github.com/ComputationalRadiationPhysics/picongpu> using a master - dev development model.

Code review is done by at least one additional code maintainer (4 eyes principle) in the dev branch and in addition by the core development team for the final release and is documented in detail here as part of the maintainer documentation. We have a style guide in place and currently use ClangFormat 11 scripts for it and general coding guidelines.

Removing old features is decided by the core development team for each new release based on ability to maintain the feature, code quality and user feedback during the weekly developer meeting, see chapter on requirements management below. We label features and pull requests and provide statistics on lines of code per release.

Our build system is based on CMAKE, we document our compiling options, build dependencies and profiles for various supercomputers to enable easy deployment using our template branch generator, see <https://picongpu.readthedocs.io/en/latest/>.

5.2 Continuous integration

We use the GitLab runners and the GitLab CI provided by the Helmholtz Software Development infrastructure (<https://www.hifis.net/services/software/helmholtzgitlab.html>). This infrastructure is available to all users with an account at one of the Helmholtz centers as well as many outside users via the Helmholtz AAI (<https://www.hifis.net/aai/>). Automatic builds and tests are done for integration in the main branch and the dev branch. The CI pipeline deploys to several different compilers, operating systems and hardware platforms (e.g. CPUs and GPUs from several vendors).

5.3 Testing

Unit testing is done regularly in the CI pipeline, while integration tests are mostly done manually for each release as well as main and dev branch merges. We are currently in the process of developing a unified test suite which will be part of the project outcomes. Physics tests of solvers and plugins are also provided within the source tree. We currently investigate the usefulness of performance test integration in the CI pipeline. Code coverage tools are not yet used, except for subprojects such as LLAMA. For specific testing on HPC systems we use PICongGPU's template batch generator.

5.4 Deployment

PICongGPU provides docker images and spack recipes for deployment as well as providing an lmod example. We provide extensive information on installing PICongGPU from source from the repository as well. For various HPC systems we provide PICongGPU profiles for the template batch generator. We plan to extend our docker images, spack recipes and PICongGPU profiles. Automatic deployment on HPC systems is currently not implemented as most systems do not provide automated access. Hardware platforms are handled by the alpaka project and I/O specifics via the openPMD project.

5.5 Documentation

We provide a user e-mail list (<https://cg.hzdr.de/Lists/picongpu-users/List.html>) that communicates changes for each new release. Furthermore, we provide inline code documentation, issue tracker via github, mailing list history, and full online documentation (<https://picongpu.readthedocs.io/en/latest/>). Documentation is available for users, developers and maintainers. We also host user workshops and provide a getting started video. We use Doxygen, Sphinx and Breathe and have versioned code documentation. We also run our own Mattermost channel for users, code developers and maintainers.

5.6 Release strategy

We release about once a year and document our release strategy for maintainers and on the repository website. PICongGPU follows a master - dev development model. That means our latest stable release is shipped in a branch called master while new and frequent changes to the code are incorporated in the development branch dev. Before drafting a

new release, we open a new release-* branch from dev with the * being the version number of the upcoming release. This branch only receives bug fixes (feature freeze) and users are welcome to try it out (however, the change log and a detailed announcement might still be missing in it). We also provide information on how to contribute on the repo website, see CONTRIBUTING.md and issues marked with ‘good first issue’ in the issue tracker on github. We host a user e-mail list and changelogs that communicate changes for each new release.

5.7 Requirements management

We have a weekly developer meeting in which we discuss and define new and existing requirements, from hardware to software to physics requirements. Additional requirements can come from the PIconGPU users via E-mail or Github issues and broken tests in the CI, e.g. with software updates in the dependencies. Prioritization is done by the core development team based on research needs, critical issues, software ecosystem and HPC platform needs, requirements on additional physics and plugins and will be matched against availability of personnel and expertise. Hardware platform requirements are mainly handled within the alpaka project.

5.8 Issue tracking

PIconGPU makes extensive use of the Github functionality and provides its own issue tracker, its own mailing list history and changelogs. Maintainers and developers have their specific roles in the issue tracking process and coding review and issue and pull request labelling rules are enforced by code maintainers. Users can add their own issues via mailing list or issue tracker. All rules are enforced by the core code maintainers and the authorization mechanisms of Github.

5.9 Dependencies/Prerequisites

A complete and up to date list of dependencies can be found in the documentation (<https://picongpu.readthedocs.io/en/latest/install/dependencies.html>). In addition, PIconGPU provides profiles, see <https://picongpu.readthedocs.io/en/latest/install/profile.html>, for HPC systems. We manage everything via CMAKE and Spack. As with all changes updating dependencies to newer versions is handled in the weekly developer meeting and is guided by the systems and their ecosystem on which PIconGPU is running as well as new software capabilities. Special care is taken for including and removing dependencies on certain C++ compilers and compute hardware specific libraries such as CUDA.

5.10 Development and Deployment towards Exascale

We have experience to work on several Top 10 HPC systems and pre-Exascale systems. From this we understand the challenges of developing and deploying PIconGPU on frontier hardware platforms. The first and foremost challenge is the availability of access to hardware with a complete and functioning software stack. Our experience tells us that

we will be facing challenges with respect to using early access machine's software stacks and, possibly, hardware issues. The best working model to account for this in our view is close collaboration with system liaisons, hardware vendors and library providers. We expect these contacts to be available during the EuroHPC phase.

For testing and developing PIConGPU, easy access to systems and fast test cycles are critical for progress in adapting the code to a new system. While we see the virtue of direct deployment and testing in a full CI/CD cycle we find that access to working compilers, message passing interfaces and I/O libraries is of even greater importance and should not be considered a given.

As such, we believe these to be necessary prerequisites for setting up a full CI/CD cycle for the code itself. We need to be able to file tickets for big reports and work closely on identifying, reporting and removing bugs with system liaisons and vendors.

We thus advocate for easy access schemes to the new machines, generous resource allocations to develop and test our codes on these machines, dedicated liaisons for EuroHPC partners for each system, close contact to the hard- and software teams of vendors and a collaborative working model between vendors, HPC administrators and application developers to create a working software ecosystems.

With these precursors in place we plan to set up a workflow for easy deployment of PIConGPU to selected EuroHPC systems.

6 Conclusion

Laser-plasma interaction at Petawatt laser class level is a frontier technology with a uniquely broad range of applications from accelerator physics, the study of laser-driven fusion, medical applications such as tumor therapy, the development of bright and compact free electron lasers to the study fundamental astrophysical phenomena in the laboratory. In this report we focus on Traveling-Wave Electron Acceleration (TWEAC) as a scalable accelerator technology towards ultra-brilliant, high-charge electron beams at TeV energies. As scalability of the PIConGPU code towards the Exascale has been demonstrated recently at the Frontier supercomputer at Oak Ridge National Laboratory, the challenge to make optimum use of upcoming hardware accelerator technologies used within EuroHPC and provided by the European Processor Initiative (EPI) will be our focus. This will be achieved by adapting the alpaka library to EPI hardware. At Exascale performance, the follow-up challenge for the PIConGPU team will be to analyze, visualize and further reuse the data from high quality simulations, e.g. for AI/ML-driven surrogate models. For this, we plan to further develop the openPMD API and strengthen the openPMD ecosystem. With PIConGPU as the central application for laser-plasma interaction studies in Helmholtz, further development in the capabilities of the code to predict the outcome of laser-plasma interaction experiments and develop applications is key to a successful research program. This goes hand in hand with enabling PIConGPU to make optimum use of future European Exascale systems.

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